

PRIVATE LABEL BRAND: UNVEILING THE KEY DRIVERS OF CONSUMERS' PURCHASE INTENTION

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this research is to provide insight on how factors such as store image, private label brand, perceived risk, price consciousness, word of mouth, perceived value, private label brand familiarity, and passion for local influence consumers' propensity to make a purchase.

Design/ Methodology/Approach: Using both digital and traditional survey methods, we were able to obtain data from 429 customers. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed using AMOS 21.

Findings: This study tested a model that incorporates Store-Image, Price Consciousness, Private Label Brand, Perceived Risk, Word of Mouth with Purchase Intention, and Vocal for Local with Purchase Intention. Hypotheses five and six were reinforced by word-of-mouth and vocal for local.

Originality/value: According to the originality of this study, PLB grocery shoppers are influenced by the appearance of the store. According to research, retail image is defined as the store's atmosphere as well as its product assortment. PLBs are used to differentiate the store's environment and its assortments. Customers ought to have a positive impression of the Private Label Brand.

Keywords: *Private Label Brand, Store-Image, Price Consciousness, Perceived Risk, Word of Mouth, Purchase Intention, and Vocal for Local*

1. INTRODUCTION

Private label brands (PLBs) endure significant modifications and enhancements. The market is currently experiencing a shift as these brands surpass the sales of well-established, well-known name brands, altering the competitive landscape of the industry (Takashima and Kim, 2021).

Private labels (Veloutsou *et al.*, 2004) store brands, and own labels (Beristain and Zorrilla, 2011; Dodd and Lindley, 2003; Arce-Urriza and Cebollada, 2012) all refer to retailer-owned brands that compete with those made by the original manufacturer. These items are made specifically for individual stores and sold in their aisles, helping to build brand recognition and customer loyalty (De Wulf *et al.*, 2005; Sharma *et al.*, 2020; Cheng *et al.*; 2007). India's retail sector could increase 15–20% in next five years. Organised and unorganised retail have private label enterprises (Beneke *et al.*, 2013). Unorganised retail—general and kirana stores, sidewalk vendors, hand-carts, vegetable and mobile vendors—controls 91% of the Indian retail market, followed by 9% of supermarkets, hypermarkets, convenience and discount stores (Sardana *et al.*, 2018). Retailers use private labels to build loyalty, improve positioning, raise margins, and lower prices. Regular PLs are mid-quality, mid-price alternatives to national brand products, while premium PLs are the best (Berges Sennou *et al.*, 2004).

Compared to other economies, where private labels enjoy a market share of more than 16% (in 2019), India had much smaller share; KPMG-RAI estimates it to be roughly 3.5%, evolved in staples (groceries) and hygiene categories enhancing the growth (Dutt, 2022). India's top Private Label product categories include apparel, hygiene, footwear, accessories, beauty, bags, watches, sunglasses, jewellery, cuisine, electronics etc. Popular PLs are Metro, More, Trends, Shoppers Stop, Pantaloons, Big Bazaar, Croma, Reliance, Westside, Bharati Retail, Nilgiris, and others are offline private label players in India. PLBs have 25–30% higher margin potential than national brands, hence several have entered the Indian market. Big Basket, Flipkart, Amazon, Fab Furnishing, First Cry, Koovs, Myntra, Snapdeal, Yepme, Zivame, Zovi, etc. are the most popular private label internet retailers in India (Sharma *et al.*, 2020). The consumer is willing to buy Private Labels if they find it of a good quality, low price, and value for money (Cotterill *et al.*, 2000). Private label food brands are globalising, this movement is changing the global food industry and how merchants, manufacturers, and consumers interact together (Lassoued and Hobbs, 2015). Store image, price consciousness (Sinha and Batra, 1999; Koschate Fischer *et al.*, 2014), perceived risk (Manikandan, 2020) and word-of-mouth (Ghorbanzadeh and Shabbir, 2023) affects the purchase intentions of the consumer for private labels. "Swadeshi" Indian private label brands are self-sufficient. Shri Narendra Modi, India's Prime Minister, promotes the "Vocal for Local" effort to buy Indian products. Indians buy Swadeshi items, which boosts our economy. Local, PLBs have increased retail demand. (Srivastava, 2020). "Vocal for Local" is the strongest slogan in 60 years. Despite all the research on PLB's purchase intentions, few studies have examined how "Vocal for Local" effect on consumer purchase intentions in India. The present study aims to fill this gap with objective to understand the importance of PLBs, and check the drivers influencing the consumers' intention to purchase the same.

2. THEORETICAL STRUCTURE AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Theoretical Structure with respect to the constructs of purchase intentions towards the private label brands of grocery is narrated through figure-1 as follows.

Figure 1: Proposed Research Framework

(Source: Author's Own Compilation)

Determinants such as Store Image, Price Consciousness, Private Label Brand, Perceived Risk, Word-of-Mouth, and Vocal for Local were examined to study its influence on consumers' purchase intention.

2.1 Purchase Intentions

The term purchase intentions (PI) was used to describe a consumer's purpose to make a purchase. Consumers' propensity to purchase a product, service, or private label brand was influenced by how they felt about it (Das, 2014). It describes what consumers expected to buy in the future in order to meet their wants and needs. Thus, individuals' purchase intentions predicted their subsequent purchases. Studies suggest that purchase intention increases the likelihood of buying (Diallo, 2012; Aurier and Lanauze, 2012).

2.2 Store Image and Purchase Intention of Private Labels

A customer's functional and psychological impression of a store is referred as Store Image (SI). The store's layout, product selection, pricing, value proposition, and customer service are functional aspect in a store. The store's environment too created its richness and appeal (Martineau, 1958). Kunkel and Berry (1968) suggested that customers develop an impression of a store by comparing it to their expectations and returning to buy more. On the other hand, store image, described by North *et al.*, (2003) as a store's identity and a determinant in first-time purchases. Consumers evaluate a store's image based on merchandise quality, ambience, assortment, convenience, and service (Beristain and Zorrilla, 2011; Dodd and Lindley, 2003; Diallo and Cliquet, 2016). Thus, store image was multi-dimensional, with many studies emphasising ambience and product selection. On the other hand, PLBs helped build store image by bringing differentiation (Labeaga *et al.*, 2007; Hoch and Banerji, 1993). Positive store image increases consumer purchasing intentions. Store image positively affects PLBs' buying intentions (Vahie and Paswan 2006; 2013; Diallo, 2012; Pilar *et al.*, 2014).

H₁₁: Store Image has a positive effect on the purchase intention of the PLBs in Grocery.

2.3 Price Consciousness and Purchase Intention of Private Labels

Price was an extrinsic cue by the 'cue utilization theory', when consumers make purchase decision.

According to Lichtenstein *et al.*, (1993), price consciousness was "the extent to which consumers were concerned exclusively with obtaining goods at lower price" with good quality. Private label purchasers prioritized cheap pricing during purchase, while value-conscious shoppers preferred lower-priced options (Palazon and Delgado, 2009; Diallo and Siqueira, 2017; Steenkamp *et al.*, 2010; Cho *et al.*, 2015). As per Santos *et al.*, (2016) cheap PLBs were more persuasive than expensive national brands. Price consciousness (PC) was linked to price sensitivity and affordability. PLBs good quality and low price attracted buyers, making them more likely to purchase the grocery (Moore and Carpenter, 2006)

H₁₂: Price Consciousness has a positive effect on the purchase intentions of the PLBs in Grocery.

2.4 Private Label Brands and Purchase Intention of Private Labels

Retailers' PLBs displayed their brand name or emblem. Retailers used best quality and pricing techniques to market their PLBs. (Geyskens *et al.*, 2010). The PLBs that consumers chose were driven by customer loyalty, market share, and competitive positioning. (Grewal *et al.*, 1998). Consumers chose PLBs due to their low prices (Diallo and Siqueira, 2017; Hultman *et al.*, 2008). The gap between the factory brands and PLBs had been narrowed due to quality improvements by PLBs (Apelbaum *et al.*, 2003). PLBs were becoming more popular due to their improved quality, affordability, and store image of the retailer leading to higher consumer's purchase intentions of grocery (Livesay and Lenon, 1978; Halstead and Ward, 1995).

H₁₃: PLBs have a positive effect on the purchase intentions of the Private label Brands in Grocery.

2.5 Perceived Risk and Purchase Intention of Private Labels

Bauer (1960) introduced the concept of perceived risk, which was characterized by ambiguity, negative and bad outcomes. Consumers were exposed to risk by choosing actions with uncertain, unpleasant effects (Wu *et al.*, 2011). The perceived risk (PR) includes financial, functional, psychological, temporal, social, physical, and total risks. (Agarwal and Teas, 2001; Semeijn *et al.*, 2004; Stone and Gronhaugh, 1993). Research showed that perceived risk affects PLBs purchases (Liljander *et al.*, 2009; Sheau-fen *et al.*, 2012) Even though there was no objective danger, perceived hazards affected PLBs buying intentions. Private brands seemed to be less risky to consumers. This showed that private label aversion may be linked to an increased sense of danger when buying food and other perishables (Benito and Partal, 2012; Richardson *et al.*, 1996; Tsiros and Heilman, 2005). Thus, previous research had established a correlation between PLB perceived risk and purchase intention, with reduced risk leading to greater intent to buy (Girard *et al.*, 2017; Nenycz-Thiel and Romaniuk, 2014; Schnittka, 2015).

H₁₄: Lower Perceived Risk have a positive effect on the purchase intentions of the PLBs in Grocery.

2.6 Word of Mouth and Purchase Intention of Private Labels

Customers acquire knowledge in both social and technological contexts. When consumers talked positively about a product or service with their friends and family, they were more likely to buy it (Hawkins *et al.*, 2004). The importance of word-of-mouth (WOM) as a result of developing client relationships has lately been highlighted in the relationship marketing literature (Nuseir, 2019). WOM communication is the informal, non-commercial exchange of information regarding products, services, or trademarks, including private labels and organisations (Birtwistle and Freathy, 1998; Walker, 2001) Hence, WOM has been a crucial channel of communication to exchange information

among consumers (Chan and Ngai, 2011; Chu & Kim, 2011; Kim *et al.*, 2014). Research showed that this sort of communication was more effective than personal selling or advertising (Engel *et al.*, 1969), and had been regarded as more reliable than institutional resources. Technology, especially mobile phones, had increased internet word of mouth (Cheung and Thadani, 2012). As a crucial marketing technique, it can influence consumer purchasing intentions and behaviours in all private labels (Avery *et al.*, 1999; Chen and Xie, 2008; Kala and Chaubey, 2018).

H15: WOM has a positive effect on the purchase intentions of the PLBs in Grocery.

2.7 Vocal for Local and Purchase Intention of Private Labels

COVID-19 prompted Shri Narendra Modi to launch Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan (Self-Reliant India campaign). India joined the global economy. On May 12, 2020, the PM introduced Aatmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyaan to minimise import dependency, enhance local production of high-value items, encourage investment, foster innovation, develop skills, safeguard IP, and create high-quality infrastructure. The government had promoted Vocal for Local (VOL) for two years. In 1905, Mahatma Gandhi's Swadeshi movement inspired this movement. It encouraged Indians to produce and be proud. (Srivastava, 2020). The local retailers made their own brands (Cheng, et al 2007 ; Dodd and Lindley, 2003), which could be treated as a *Swadeshi Brand*. Thus, the concept of *Vocal for Local* went in tandem with the concept of PLB. Private label shoppers' preference for local brands backed the PM's view. VOL increased private label grocery purchases, according to reviews. Marketing experts tested VOL products for reliability.

H16: VOL has a positive effect on the purchase intentions of the PLBd in Grocery.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Variables and measurement scale development

On a seven-point Likert scale ranging from "Extremely disagree" to "Extremely agree," participants were asked to rate their level of agreement with a variety of propositions. The questionnaire requested both personal and quantitative information regarding the factors that influenced consumer's purchase decisions. Location, age, gender, education, occupation, and monthly income were included in the demographic data.

Table 1: Items Used In Construction Of Construct

Construct	Descriptor	Number of Items	Adapted From
Store Image	SI	13 Items	Mostafa and Elseidi (2018), Wu et al., (2011), Calvo and Mangin (2016)
Price Consciousness	PC	7 Items	Mostafa and Elseidi (2018), Wu et al., (2011), Calvo and Mangin (2016)
Private Label Brand Image	PLB	2 Items	Mostafa and Elseidi (2018)
Perceived Risk	PR	7 Items	Wu et al., (2011)
Word of Mouth	WOM	6 Items	Ismail and Spinelli (2012)
Vocal for Local	VOL	9 Items	Framed from Literature and Validated from Experts
Purchase Intention	PI	8 Items	Mostafa and Elseidi (2018); Wu et al., (2011); Calvo and Mangin (2016); and Konuk (2018)

(Source: Compiled by Researchers)

3.2 Sampling and fieldwork

The study was conducted in the urban area of Gujarat (Gandhinagar), Madhya Pradesh (Indore), and Maharashtra (Pune). The population of the research consisted of families dwelling in city. According to the 2011 census conducted by the Directorate of Census Operations, there were 28,224 homes in Gandhinagar city. The number of households in Cities of Indore and Pune have 4,90,140 and 13,71,531 households, respectively (India Growing, n.d.). There was a combined total of 18,89,895 households across the three cities. With a 95% confidence interval and a 5% error of margin, the sample size was calculated to be 384 homes. There were 52 items, used in the study. Based on the number of items, the formula to determine the sample size was $52 \times 5 + 50 = 310$ (Gaskin, 2023). The researchers, to be on the safer side, decided to take a sample size on the higher side i.e. 500. The sample size was determined using the, formula $n = Z^2 \cdot p \cdot q / e^2$, i.e. $(1.96)^2 \cdot (0.5) (0.5) / (0.05)^2$. If the sample size $N > 200$ (the rule of thumb), then it was not only treated as feasible but also justified the power of the statistical test (Kyriazos, 2018). The questionnaire was filled by a family head or adult. To assess measuring scales and questionnaire language understanding, 30 respondents were pilot-tested. The questionnaire took 10 minutes. The survey was conducted in October 2022–January 2023.

All three researchers used a mixed method of a paper-pencil and online survey to elicit the response in large numbers. The respondent was given the questionnaire, to avoid response bias (De Jong *et al*, 2016). Based on the Mahalanobis Distances method, where the probability values were less than 0.001, the responses of such 40 respondents were treated as outliers and dropped from the survey (Statistics Solutions, n.d.). 20 respondents did not fill out the questionnaire completely, such missed responses were removed from the study. 11 respondents provided the same-liner answers, which were also removed from the study. Thus, the final usable sample size in the study was 429, depicting an 81% response rate.

Table 2: Demographic Details

Parameter	Count	Percentage
Location		
Gandhinagar	143	33
Indore	143	33
Pune	143	34
Gender		
Male	211	49
Female	218	51
Age		
18-25 Years	50	12
26-30 Years	106	25
31-35 Years	100	23
36-40 Years	104	24
41 and Above	69	16
Education		
Less than Graduate	15	03
Graduate	205	48
Post-Graduate	209	49
Occupation		
Salaried	214	50

Parameter	Count	Percentage
Retired	10	02
Business	90	21
Home-Maker	115	27
Monthly Income (Rs.)		
Less than Rs.30,000	153	36
Rs.30,001-Rs.50,000	120	28
Above Rs.50,001	156	36

(Source: Primary Data)

A quota sampling technique was used for selecting the number of respondents across each location. The number of female respondents was more than the number of male respondents. The highest 25% of respondents were in the age group of 26-30 years. Most of the respondent had post-graduation degrees. 50% of respondents belonged to the salaried class. Only 28% of the respondents had a monthly income between Rs.30, 001 to Rs.50,000.

Analysis of the Measurement Model

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics and Normality Statistics

Item Code	Mean	SD	Skweness	Kurtosis
SI3	5.17	1.49	-0.85	0.44
SI4	5.53	1.29	-0.91	0.83
SI5	5.19	1.42	-0.63	-0.10
SI6	5.79	1.13	-1.03	1.42
SI9	5.70	1.19	-1.02	1.24
SI10	5.42	1.23	-0.87	0.99
SI11	5.23	1.29	-0.59	0.22
SI12	5.41	1.27	-0.73	0.32
SI13	5.59	1.39	-1.08	0.97
PC1	4.67	1.72	-0.66	0.32
PC2	4.29	1.86	-0.86	0.53
PC3	4.66	1.61	-0.42	-0.63
PC4	4.95	1.62	-0.42	-0.72
PC5	5.10	1.35	-0.46	-0.73
PC6	5.12	1.27	-0.77	0.28
PC7	4.54	1.56	-0.51	-0.67
PLB1	5.11	1.32	-0.51	-0.46
PLB2	5.15	1.43	-0.59	-0.41
PR1	4.43	1.68	-0.62	-0.41
PR2	4.39	1.71	-0.29	-0.96
PR3	4.33	1.74	-0.44	-0.47
PR4	4.82	1.50	-0.65	-0.16
PR5	4.49	1.74	-0.59	0.14
PR6	4.46	1.63	-0.58	0.16
PR7	4.71	1.65	-0.46	-0.43
WOM1	5.18	1.39	-0.72	0.48
WOM2	5.22	1.37	-0.79	0.56
WOM3	5.25	1.34	-0.81	0.75
WOM4	5.25	1.50	-1.02	1.00
WOM5	5.23	1.42	-0.84	0.45

Item Code	Mean	SD	Skweness	Kurtosis
WOM6	5.31	1.32	-0.84	0.75
VOL1	5.50	1.30	-0.92	0.94
VOL2	5.70	1.28	-1.04	1.13
VOL3	5.66	1.38	-1.15	1.19
VOL4	5.75	1.28	-1.15	1.51
VOL5	5.71	1.27	-1.21	1.81
VOL6	5.72	1.25	-1.03	1.01
VOL7	5.71	1.26	-1.05	1.15
VOL8	5.74	1.30	-1.07	0.97
VOL9	5.73	1.27	-1.18	1.55
PI1	5.34	1.31	-0.71	0.33
PI2	5.31	1.30	-0.81	0.68
PI3	5.47	1.26	-0.78	0.44
PI4	5.40	1.26	-0.70	0.31
PI5	5.28	1.36	-0.84	0.57
PI6	5.19	1.39	-0.76	0.30
PI7	5.20	1.41	-0.82	0.45
PI8	5.16	1.41	-0.87	0.67

(Source: SPSS Output)

In the process of estimating the mean, SD, skewness, and kurtosis, it was observed that the skewness and kurtosis were in the range of -3 to +3, which indicated normality (Gaskin, 2023). An item with codes SI1 and SI7 was dropped at this stage because it fell beyond the specified range, and there were normality issues. Dropping the items SI1 and SI7, did not make the construct under-identified, because the number of items measuring the construct was more.

Reliability Testing and Analysis of Measurement Model

For assessing the reliability of the scale and internal consistency, Cronbach Alpha values were computed in SPSS. The α coefficient was greater than the standard value of 0.6 for all the constructs (Hair *et al*, 2010). It lay in the range of 0.76 to 0.94. The α coefficient for all 48 items, finally used in the analysis was 0.95.

Table 4: CFA and Cronbach Alpha Values

Item Code	Factor Loadings	R-Square	P-Value	Cronbach Alpha
SI3	0.63	0.39	***	0.89
SI4	0.90	0.80	***	
SI5	0.78	0.61	***	
SI6	0.65	0.43	***	
SI9	0.81	0.66	***	
SI10	0.76	0.58	***	
SI11	0.75	0.56	***	
SI12	0.80	0.64	***	
SI13	0.62	0.39	***	
PC1	0.73	0.53	***	
PC2	0.74	0.55	***	
PC3	0.73	0.54	***	
PC4	0.73	0.53	***	
PC5	0.83	0.69	***	

Item Code	Factor Loadings	R-Square	P-Value	Cronbach Alpha
PC6	0.85	0.73	***	
PC7	0.69	0.48	***	
PLB1	0.87	0.76	***	0.76
PLB2	0.71	0.50	***	
PR1	0.62	0.38	***	0.88
PR2	0.78	0.61	***	
PR3	0.75	0.56	***	
PR4	0.70	0.49	***	
PR5	0.74	0.55	***	
PR6	0.75	0.57	***	
PR7	0.69	0.48	***	
WOM1	0.83	0.68	***	0.94
WOM2	0.85	0.73	***	
WOM3	0.85	0.73	***	
WOM4	0.86	0.73	***	
WOM5	0.84	0.70	***	
WOM6	0.85	0.72	***	
VOL1	0.61	0.38	***	0.94
VOL2	0.76	0.57	***	
VOL3	0.85	0.73	***	
VOL4	0.85	0.72	***	
VOL5	0.82	0.67	***	
VOL6	0.85	0.72	***	
VOL7	0.86	0.74	***	
VOL8	0.83	0.68	***	
VOL9	0.75	0.56	***	
PI1	0.80	0.65	***	0.93
PI2	0.77	0.59	***	
PI3	0.83	0.69	***	
PI4	0.84	0.70	***	
PI5	0.82	0.68	***	
PI6	0.80	0.64	***	
PI7	0.84	0.70	***	
PI8	0.71	0.50	***	

(Source: SPSS Output)

Tools for Data Analysis

Using SPSS 20.0, mean, median, mode, percentage, frequency count, skewness, and kurtosis were calculated for an item of the construct and the construct itself. Mahalanobis SPSS calculated outlier distances and inter-item correlations. SPSS measured the construct Cronbach Alpha coefficient to ensure item reliability. Outer and inner collinearity statistics were measured by computing VIF and Tolerance in SPSS. Using the Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS 21.0), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was applied. Reliability, convergent validity, and divergent validity examined measurement adequacy. MSV, ASV, AVE, Composite Reliability (CR), Discriminant Value, and HTMT Ratio were used in study.

Figure 2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis

(Source: AMOS Output)

Analysis of the Measurement Model

The CFA model using AMOS displayed the store image as a second-order factor comprising two sub-factors i.e. Assortment (consisting of 2 items) and Ambience (consisting of 7 items). The items SI2 and SI8 had strong cross-loading issues, and hence were dropped from the analysis, at the CFA stage itself. Price Consciousness was also regarded as a second-order factor comprising two sub-factors i.e. Price Sensitivity (comprising of 4 items), and Affordability (consisting of 3 items). Rest all the items of the constructs loaded on their respective constructs only. The first-order factors consisted of PLB Image, Perceived Risk, WOM, VOL and Purchase Intention. The second-order construct and the first-order construct each had clean loadings.

Table 5: Construct’s Correlation Coefficients and Discriminant Validity

Construct	X	SD	CR	AVE	MSV	ASV	SI	PC	PLB	PR	WOM	VOL	PI
SI	5.45	0.95	0.81	0.68	0.53	0.40	0.82						
PC	4.76	1.11	0.70	0.54	0.61	0.40	0.68	0.80					
PLB	5.13	1.24	0.77	0.63	0.28	0.18	0.72	0.59	0.79				
PR	4.52	1.28	0.88	0.52	0.06	0.04	0.21	0.63	0.28	0.72			
WOM	5.24	1.21	0.94	0.72	0.57	0.39	0.73	0.78	0.53	0.25	0.85		
VOL	5.69	1.06	0.94	0.64	0.37	0.37	0.61	0.42	0.34	0.09	0.47	0.80	
PI	5.29	1.11	0.93	0.64	0.57	0.36	0.68	0.70	0.49	0.22	0.76	0.61	0.80

Reliability of the Construct and Validity Estimates

The instrument's dependability measures the targeted latent construct. Cronbach Alpha measured

instrument internal reliability. Reliability testing was conducted during the pilot testing, before the survey. The study measured reliability and internal consistency using Composite Reliability (CR), the most popular tool. To calculate the construct's average variation, AVE was calculated. When all measurement model components were significant, AVE measured the tool's convergent validity. The model's tool was checked for redundant items using discriminant validity (DV). The study measured DV using MSV and ASV. Discriminant validity proved the constructs were unrelated (Zhu, 2000).

The average of the seven constructs was closer to five, the SD of each construct was near one, indicating a minor response dispersion. All latent constructs had CRs over 0.60, indicating internal reliability and consistency (Bagozzi and Yi, 1988). Similarly, the AVE of all the seven constructs was greater than 0.5, representing the test of convergent validity and internal consistency (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). To verify discriminant validity, MSV, ASV, and AVE were compared, all constructs except one had MSV and ASV less than AVE, indicating discriminant validity issues. The diagonal values (square root of AVE) for each construct were bigger than the correlation coefficient (r) for each pair of constructs, validating the DV. DV was checked using the latest HTMT ratio. The HTMT ratio assessed hetrotrait and monotrait. If HTMT was less than 0.90, two reflective constructs were discriminant.

Table 6: Correlation Table of the Construct

Construct1	Relation	Construct2	R
Store Image			
Price_Consciousness	<-->	Store_Image	0.68
Store_Image	<-->	Private_Label_Brand	0.72
Store_Image	<-->	Perceived_Risk	0.21
Store_Image	<-->	Word_Of_Mouth	0.73
Store_Image	<-->	Vocal_For_Local	0.61
Store_Image	<-->	Purchase_Intention	0.68
Price Consciousness			
Price_Consciousness	<-->	Private_Label_Brand	0.59
Price_Consciousness	<-->	Perceived_Risk	0.63
Price_Consciousness	<-->	Word_Of_Mouth	0.78
Price_Consciousness	<-->	Vocal_For_Local	0.42
Price_Consciousness	<-->	Purchase_Intention	0.70
Private Label Brand			
Private_Label_Brand	<-->	Perceived_Risk	0.28
Private_Label_Brand	<-->	Word_Of_Mouth	0.53
Private_Label_Brand	<-->	Vocal_For_Local	0.34
Private_Label_Brand	<-->	Purchase_Intention	0.49
Perceived Risk			
Perceived_Risk	<-->	Word_Of_Mouth	0.25
Perceived_Risk	<-->	Vocal_For_Local	0.09
Perceived_Risk	<-->	Purchase_Intention	0.22
Word of Mouth			
Word_Of_Mouth	<-->	Vocal_For_Local	0.47
Word_Of_Mouth	<-->	Purchase_Intention	0.76
Vocal for Local			
Vocal_For_Local	<-->	Purchase_Intention	0.61
Purchase Intention			
Store_Image	<-->	Purchase_Intention	0.68

Construct1	Relation	Construct2	R
Price_Consciousness	<-->	Purchase_Intention	0.70
Private_Label_Brand	<-->	Purchase_Intention	0.49
Perceived_Risk	<-->	Purchase_Intention	0.22
Word_Of_Mouth	<-->	Purchase_Intention	0.76
Vocal_For_Local	<-->	Purchase_Intention	0.61

(Source: Excel Computation)

Table 7: Hetrotrait and Monotrait Ratio

Construct	SI	PC	PLB	PR	WOM	VOL
SI						
PC	0.50					
PLB	0.67	0.49				
PR	0.22	0.63	0.26			
WOM	0.68	0.62	0.53	0.26		
VOL	0.58	0.31	0.35	0.11	0.48	
PI	0.63	0.54	0.51	0.24	0.75	0.61

(Source: Excel Computation)

As observed the HTMT ratio values were less than 0.90, so there was no DV issue. All the constructs were neither correlated nor similar to each other. Thus, the singular identity of each construct was established. The uni-dimensionality, convergent validity, construct validity, discriminant validity, internal reliability, composite reliability, AVE, MSV, ASV, and HTMT ratio falls in the line with the benchmark value, indicating a good fit of the model.

Analysis of the Structural Model

The multicollinearity statistics and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was checked, from the dimensions of outer values and inner values before running the SEM model.

Table 8: Inner and Outer Collinearity Statistics

Items	Tolerance	VIF	Item	Tolerance	VIF
SI3	0.67	1.49	SI4	0.51	1.96
SI5	0.57	1.75	SI6	0.40	2.52
SI9	0.39	2.57	SI10	0.46	2.18
SI11	0.46	2.18	SI12	0.40	2.52
SI13	0.64	1.56	PC1	0.52	1.92
PC2	0.47	2.13	PC3	0.53	1.88
PC4	0.52	1.93	PC5	0.43	2.34
PC6	0.44	2.26	PC7	0.64	1.57
PLB1	0.62	1.62	PLB2	0.32	1.62
PR1	0.62	1.62	PR2	0.41	2.43
PR3	0.47	2.13	PR4	0.57	1.75
PR5	0.50	2.00	PR6	0.43	2.32
PR7	0.51	1.96	WOM1	0.33	3.04
WOM2	0.29	3.40	WOM3	0.32	3.16
WOM4	0.29	3.40	WOM5	0.32	3.11
WOM6	0.34	2.92	VOL1	0.63	1.58
VOL2	0.45	2.24	VOL3	0.28	3.56

Items	Tolerance	VIF	Item	Tolerance	VIF
VOL4	0.29	3.44	VOL5	0.35	2.87
VOL6	0.31	3.25	VOL7	0.29	3.44
VOL8	0.35	2.83	VOL9	0.46	2.19
Store Image	0.46	2.17	Price Consciousness	0.52	1.93
Perceived Risk	0.69	1.45	Private Label Brand	0.66	1.51
Word of Mouth	0.51	1.97	Vocal for Local	0.69	1.45

(Source: SPSS Output)

There was no multicollinearity problem between the independent variable, because the outer and inner tolerance value was more than 0.20, and the VIF value was less than 5.00.

Figure 3: Structural Model

(Source: AMOS Output)

AMOS software was used to run the structural equation model. The model would be a good-fitting model if the value of CMIN/df was less than 5. The GFI indices, TLI index; CFI index was more than 0.90, RMSEA was between 0.05 and 0.08. The fit indices for the model, CMIN/df= 2.14; GFI=0.91; TLI=0.91; CFI=0.92 and RMSEA=0.05. The squared multiple correlation was 0.69 for purchase intention. This showed that 69 % of variance in purchase intention was accounted by SI, PC, PLB, PR, WOM and VOL.

The study assessed the impact of SI, PC, PLB, PR, WOM, and VOL on PI. The impact of SI was positive but insignificant (b=0.01, t=0.11, p=0.91), hence H₁₁ was not supported. The impact of PC was positive but insignificant (b=0.38, t=1.71, p=0.09), hence H₁₂ was not supported. The impact of PLB

was positive but insignificant ($b=0.03$, $t=0.40$, $p=0.69$), hence H_{13} was not supported. The impact of PR was negative but insignificant ($b=-0.14$, $t=-1.30$, $p=0.20$), hence H_{14} was not supported. The impact of WOM was positive and significant ($b=0.33$, $t=2.55$, $p=0.01$), hence H_{15} was supported. The impact of VOL was positive and significant ($b=0.29$, $t=5.40$, $p=0.00$), hence H_{16} was supported. Model fit indices and hypothesis results are presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Results of SEM

Hypothesis	Hypothesized Relationship	Standardized Estimates	t-value	p-value	Decision
H11: Greater store image results in higher purchase intention.	Store-Image->Purchase Intention	0.01	0.11	0.91	Not Significant
H12: Greater price consciousness of PLB results in higher purchase intention.	Price Consciousness->Purchase Intention	0.38	1.71	0.09	Not Significant
H13: Greater PLB's image results in higher purchase intention.	Private Label Brand->Purchase Intention	0.03	0.40	0.69	Not Significant
H14: Lower perceived risk of PLB results in higher purchase intention.	Perceived Risk->Purchase Intention	-0.14	-1.30	0.20	Not Significant
H15: Higher Word of Mouth results in higher purchase intention.	Word of Mouth->Purchase Intention	0.33	2.55	0.01	Significant
H16: Higher vocal for local thought results in higher purchase intention.	Vocal for Local->Purchase Intention	0.29	5.40	0.00	Significant
R-Square					
Purchase Intention: 69%					
Model Fit					
CMIN/df= 2.14; GFI=0.91; TLI=0.91; CFI=0.92 and RMSEA=0.05					

(Source: Compiled by Researchers)

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The present study examined a model that integrates number of variables pertaining to purchasing intention, Store-Image, Price Consciousness, Private Label Brand, Perceived Risk, Word of Mouth with Purchase Intention, and Vocal for Local with Purchase Intention. Findings for Hypotheses five and six was significant for WOM and VOL which supported PI. The r value was 0.76 between WOM and PI and it was 0.61 between VOL and PI.

5. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

According to the research, Word of Mouth (WOM), a key marketing tactic, can influence consumer buy intentions and behaviour in all types of private labels (Avery et al., 1999; Chen and Xie, 2008). For WOM, retailers must promote PLBs on Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, and other platforms. PLBs' availability on Grofers, Amazon, Flipkart, Blink it, and other online shopping platforms and customer reviews might enhance WOM. VOL encourages local brands and small retailers. VOL boosted groceries Private Label purchases. For the cause of self-reliance and Aatmanirbhar Bharat customers may support retailers by purchasing local PLBs.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The present study is not exempted from limitations. In first place, this study analyses PLBs focusing on purchase intention and other variables. PLBs sold across India may be considered in further research. Finally, it would be advisable to develop further analysis incorporating other variables that influence consumer behaviour with food private label brands, such as perceived quality, or social and psychological variables. Thus, generalizations to other product categories may be made with caution.

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